

Design of fiber reinforced composite laminates and discussion on feasible region of lamination parameters

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Abstract: The relationship of parameters in material property need to be known in simultaneous design optimization of material and structure, thus the obtained materials can be explained in physics. The relations of stiffness properties in fiber reinforced composite laminates can be defined by 12 lamination parameters of in-plane, coupling and out-of-plane stiffness. At present, the obtained feasible region of 12 lamination parameters is necessary condition but not sufficient for laminate materials which can be realized in physics. In this paper, the change of feasible region of 12 lamination parameters with the increase of the number of plies was studied firstly under the assumption that the laminate thickness is fixed, the angles and thicknesses of ply can be changed arbitrary. We found that the feasible region is essentially unchanged when the number of plies is more than 6 plies. Then by considering least(6 plies) ply angles and ply thickness and fiber volume fraction in micro configuration as design variables, a topology optimization based method is proposed to minimize compliance of laminates under the condition of given fiber volume ratio. Finally, numerical examples are presented to demonstrate the validity of the proposed approach.

Keywords: *lamination parameters, laminates optimization, feasible region*

1 Introduction

One of the basic purposes of structural engineering optimization is to find a stiffest structure with a given volume which is able to bear more loadings under the conditions of a given set of boundary conditions and loads. Simultaneous optimization of structures and materials is known as the optimal design to achieve this purpose. It not only could optimize material distribution in space but also could design elastic property of local materials. The property of local materials is not limited except ensuring material can be realized in physics [1-4]. The difficulty of simultaneous optimization of structures and materials is the optimal results can't be realized easily in physics. On one hand, continuous variability of material property in design domain makes material manufacture inconvenience; on the other hand, parameters in material property relate to each other and it is difficult to determine the range of each parameter. Therefore, the obtained materials can't be ensured to realize by physical materials.

For fiber reinforced laminates, the elastic stiffness can be denoted by 12 lamination parameters and invariants [5], lamination parameters represent lay-up of laminates (ply angles, ply thickness and number of plies). As parameters of elastic stiffness must have some relations, then the 12 lamination parameters also have the same case. In other word, the feasible region of lamination parameters must be determined in order to ensure lamination parameters

corresponding to laminate lay-up. The feasible region for in-plane or out-of-plane lamination parameters has been given in analytical form by [6]. However, feasible region for 12 lamination parameters has not analytical expressions because of their complexity. Literature [7-9] provided methods to obtain approximate feasible region, and expressions for describe the region were given by [9], but the literature also indicated that these expressions are necessary but not sufficient conditions for realizing material in physics.

Literature [6] concluded that an optimal design can be realized with at most two plies for pure membrane problems under the condition of laminate thickness is fixed, but ply angles and ply thickness can be changed arbitrary. Inspired by this idea, in this paper, the change of feasible region with 12 lamination parameters was discussed by increasing the number of plies, and solved the least plies for feasible region when it is essentially unchanged. Then ply angles and ply thickness are treated as variables in optimization problems for design laminate lay-up with the given plies. In this case, the optimal material can be obtained and also be ensured to realize in physics. The relationship of parameters in material property is not needed, so the difficulty of feasible region of lamination parameters is avoided.

This paper is organized as follows. Firstly, the least plies for satisfying the feasible region of 12 lamination parameters was determined. Then, a topology optimization formulation for simultaneously

designing lay-up and fiber distribution is proposed. The least number of fiber angles and ply thickness, and fiber volume fraction in micro lay-up are determined simultaneously to minimize compliance of laminates with given fiber volume ratio. For the sake of manufacturability, the micro lay-up is assumed to the same in laminates. Finally, numerical examples are presented to demonstrate the validity of the proposed approach.

2 lamination parameters

In the first-order shear deformation theory, the constitutive equations for the laminated are expressed in the form as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \\ Q \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B & 0 \\ B & D & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & H \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon^0 \\ \kappa \\ \gamma^0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where N , M and Q are the stress, moment, and transverse shear stress resultants, respectively; ε^0 , κ and γ^0 are the strains, the curvatures at the midplane, and the transverse shear strains, respectively; and A , B , D , H are the in-plane, coupling, out-of-plane, and shear stiffness, respectively. The stiffness components A_{ij} , B_{ij} , $D_{ij}(i,j=1,2,6)$, $H_{ij}(i,j=1,2)$, can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{22} \\ A_{12} \\ A_{66} \\ A_{16} \\ A_{26} \end{Bmatrix} = h \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1^A & \xi_3^A & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_1^A & \xi_3^A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_3^A & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_3^A & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \xi_2^A / 2 & \xi_4^A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_2^A / 2 & -\xi_4^A & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} B_{11} \\ B_{22} \\ B_{12} \\ B_{66} \\ B_{16} \\ B_{26} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{h^2}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \xi_1^B & \xi_3^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\xi_1^B & \xi_3^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_3^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_3^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_2^B / 2 & \xi_4^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_2^B / 2 & -\xi_4^B & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} D_{11} \\ D_{22} \\ D_{12} \\ D_{66} \\ D_{16} \\ D_{26} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{h^3}{12} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1^D & \xi_3^D & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_1^D & \xi_3^D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_3^D & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_3^D & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \xi_2^D / 2 & \xi_4^D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_2^D / 2 & -\xi_4^D & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} H_{11} \\ H_{22} \\ H_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = h \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1^A \\ 1 & -\xi_1^A \\ 0 & -\xi_2^A \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_6 \\ U_7 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Where h is the thickness of laminate. U_i ($i=1, \dots, 7$) are stiffness invariants which indicate material property in each ply are the same, defined as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{3}{8} & \frac{3}{8} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{8} & \frac{1}{8} & -\frac{1}{4} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{8} & \frac{1}{8} & \frac{3}{4} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{8} & \frac{1}{8} & -\frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{11} \\ Q_{22} \\ Q_{12} \\ Q_{66} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} U_6 \\ U_7 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{44} \\ Q_{55} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= E_{11}/(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}), Q_{22} = E_{22}/(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ Q_{12} &= \nu_{12}Q_{22} = \nu_{21}Q_{11}, Q_{66} = G_{12}, Q_{44} = G_{23} \\ Q_{55} &= G_{31} = G_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (8), E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} , ν_{12} are engineering constants of a unidirectional laminate, and defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= E_m + (E_f - E_m)V_f \\ E_{22} &= \frac{E_f E_m}{E_f + (E_m - E_f)V_f} \\ \nu_{12} &= \nu_m + (\nu_f - \nu_m)V_f, \nu_{21} = \frac{E_2}{E_1}\nu_{12}, \\ G_{12} &= \frac{G_f G_m}{G_f + (G_m - G_f)V_f} \\ G_{23} &= G_f V_f + G_m V_m = G_m + (G_f - G_m)V_f \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In Eqs.(2-4), $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A$, $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^B$, $\xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^D$ are the in-plane, coupling, and out-of-plane lamination parameters, respectively, and expressed by numerical integration as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A &= \sum_{k=1}^n (z_k - z_{k-1}) [\cos 2\theta_k, \sin 2\theta_k, \cos 4\theta_k, \sin 4\theta_k] \\ \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^B &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^n (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) [\cos 2\theta_k, \sin 2\theta_k, \cos 4\theta_k, \sin 4\theta_k] \\ \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^D &= 4 \sum_{k=1}^n (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) [\cos 2\theta_k, \sin 2\theta_k, \cos 4\theta_k, \sin 4\theta_k] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $\theta(z)$ is the fiber orientation angles through the normalized thickness z . The lamination parameters satisfy inequality:

$$-1 \leq \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^{A,B,D} \leq 1 \quad (11)$$

3 Relations between lamination parameters and number of plies

Theoretically, the feasible region of lamination parameters can be expanded with increasing number of plies, and converged to maximum region. Thus constructed following function:

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^4 (k_i^A \xi_i^A + k_i^B \xi_i^B + k_i^D \xi_i^D) \quad (12)$$

Where

$$\sum_{i=1}^4 [(k_i^A)^2 + (k_i^B)^2 + (k_i^D)^2] = 1 \quad (13)$$

In a geometrical interpretation, F is a hyperplane whose unit normal is $s(k_1^A, \dots, k_4^A, \dots, k_1^B, \dots, k_4^B, k_1^D, \dots, k_4^D)$, the lamination parameters in function F are defined by fiber angles and ply thickness with the given number of plies. Because of the feasible region of lamination parameters is a convex domain, the hyperplane arrives at boundary of feasible region when F is maximized for a given vector s , the value of F denotes the boundary point. When any directional vector s which satisfied Eq.(13) are given, utilizing the maximum value of F can describe the boundary of feasible region.

In order to find the relationship between boundary of feasible region and number of plies, the optimization problem could be constructed as follows: For given a vector s ,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Find } \mathbf{x} = [n, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_n, z_1, \dots, z_n] \\ & \max_{\mathbf{x}} F_n(\mathbf{x}) \\ & \text{s.t. } 0 \leq \theta_j \leq \pi \\ & \quad -0.5 \leq z_j \leq 0.5 \\ & \quad z_j - z_{j+1} + \beta \leq 0 \\ & \quad j = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where z is normalized coordinate through laminate thickness, and the range is $z \in [-0.5, 0.5]$. $z_1 = -0.5$, $z_{n+1} = 0.5$, n is the number of plies, β is a small positive number which is brought to avoid vanish ply thickness caused by the superposition through z direction along thickness. Here $\beta = 0.001$.

Solving problem (14), firstly, a directional vector s should be designated, and s could be any vector under the pre-condition of satisfying Eq.(13); se-

condly, using ply angle and ply thickness as design variables to solve problem (14) by differential evolution method [10,11] for a given number of plies value n , and the function F will get its extreme value which is a point in the feasible region.

In order to discuss the change of feasible region along with the increasing of the number of plies, uniform experimental design method [12,13] was adopted to construct a set of directional vector $S = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{16}]^T$ (see appendix). The convergence of the feasible region was determined by the maximum values of 16 point in the boundary with increasing number of plies. Table 1 shows the calculated maximum values of function F with a given s_i under the condition of different number of plies. The relative errors of F with different number of plies are shown in table 2 to further illustrate the change of feasible region.

Table 1 the maximum value of F and number of layers

F value	2 layers	3 layers	4 layers	5 layers	6 layers	7 layers	10 layers	20 layers
$F(s_1)$	0.5551	0.7100	0.7315	0.7363	0.7382	0.7392	0.7405	0.7416
$F(s_2)$	1.2065	1.2209	1.2317	1.2347	1.2366	1.2376	1.2391	1.2401
$F(s_3)$	1.5863	1.5863	1.5864	1.5864	1.5864	1.5864	1.5864	1.5864
$F(s_4)$	1.2878	1.3009	1.3074	1.3120	1.3140	1.3150	1.3170	1.3185
$F(s_5)$	0.8700	0.9890	0.9907	0.9910	0.9911	0.9912	0.9914	0.9915
$F(s_6)$	1.4306	1.4337	1.4345	1.4349	1.4352	1.4354	1.4356	1.4358
$F(s_7)$	1.3787	1.3845	1.3894	1.3917	1.3926	1.3934	1.3945	1.3953
$F(s_8)$	1.2311	1.2331	1.2354	1.2361	1.2364	1.2367	1.2370	1.2374
$F(s_9)$	0.7568	1.0194	1.0273	1.0311	1.0326	1.0338	1.0351	1.0361
$F(s_{10})$	1.0297	1.0711	1.0732	1.0744	1.0755	1.0759	1.0769	1.0776
$F(s_{11})$	1.2513	1.2641	1.2659	1.2675	1.2680	1.2683	1.2686	1.2690
$F(s_{12})$	1.2136	1.2218	1.2286	1.2304	1.2318	1.2323	1.2330	1.2334
$F(s_{13})$	1.1733	1.2175	1.2311	1.2371	1.2404	1.2424	1.2451	1.2471
$F(s_{14})$	1.0916	1.0940	1.0947	1.0947	1.0948	1.0948	1.0949	1.0949
$F(s_{15})$	0.8854	0.9435	0.9487	0.9512	0.9529	0.9536	0.9550	0.9558
$F(s_{16})$	0.3712	0.7299	0.7358	0.7386	0.7406	0.7417	0.7432	0.7444

Table 2 relative error of F with different number of layers

(\times 100%)	(F_2^-/F_3^-)	(F_3^-/F_4^-)	(F_4^-/F_5^-)	(F_5^-/F_6^-)	(F_6^-/F_7^-)	(F_{10}^-/F_{10}^-)	(F_{20}^-/F_{20}^-)
s_1	21.8%	2.94%	0.65%	0.26%	0.14%	0.18%	0.15%
s_2	1.18%	0.88%	0.24%	0.15%	0.08%	0.12%	0.08%
s_3	0	0.01%	0	0	0	0	0
s_4	1.01%	0.50%	0.35%	0.15%	0.08%	0.15%	0.11%
s_5	12.0%	0.17%	0.03%	0.01%	0.01%	0.02%	0.01%
s_6	0.22%	0.06%	0.03%	0.02%	0.01%	0.01%	0.01%
s_7	0.42%	0.35%	0.17%	0.06%	0.06%	0.08%	0.06%
s_8	0.16%	0.19%	0.06%	0.02%	0.02%	0.02%	0.03%
s_9	25.8%	0.77%	0.37%	0.15%	0.12%	0.13%	0.10%
s_{10}	3.87%	0.20%	0.11%	0.10%	0.04%	0.09%	0.06%
s_{11}	1.01%	0.14%	0.13%	0.04%	0.02%	0.02%	0.03%
s_{12}	0.67%	0.55%	0.15%	0.11%	0.04%	0.06%	0.03%
s_{13}	3.63%	1.10%	0.49%	0.27%	0.16%	0.21%	0.16%
s_{14}	0.22%	0.06%	0	0.01%	0	0.01%	0
s_{15}	6.16%	0.55%	0.26%	0.18%	0.07%	0.15%	0.08%
s_{16}	49.1%	0.80%	0.38%	0.27%	0.15%	0.20%	0.16%
Max	49.1%	2.94%	0.65%	0.27%	0.16%	0.21%	0.16%

Table 2 has shown that the maximum relative error was only 0.27% compared the result of 6 plies with that of 5 plies. Comparing the result of 7 plies with that of 6 plies, the maximum relative error was reduced to 0.16%. The relative errors were stabilization with the increasing of the number of plies. The

calculated results indicated that the feasible region essentially reached the maximum range once the number of plies is 5. As there is no rigorous proof to verify the conclusion theoretically, 6 plies is used to approximate the maximum feasible region range in order to ensure the approximate range to equal or less than maximum feasible region. Thus, utilizing 6 plies to optimize the problem can ensure the optimal results to be realized in physics.

4 Optimization formulation

According with the above analysis, the micro lay-up with 6 plies was adopted. Fiber volume distribution in laminate and ply angles, ply thickness and fiber volume fraction in micro lay-up were simultaneously optimized under the condition of laminate thickness is fixed. For manufacturing conveniently, the same micro lay-up configuration was assumed in laminate.

Finite element method was used to obtain the structural response, design variables were fiber volume ratio in element and ply angles θ_i , normalized coordinate z_j ($i=1, \dots, 6; j=1, \dots, 5$). In optimization, the maximum limit value of fiber volume fraction in element was ρ_{fmax} , here $\rho_{fmax} = 0.4$. P was used to denote macro density to control the configuration distribution in design domain.

To design a structure with maximum stiffness under a given static loading, the compliance is adopted as the objective function. The compliance C is expressed as

$$C = \int_{\Omega} f_i u_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} t_i u_i ds = FU \quad (15)$$

where, consider a general body Ω subjected to applied body forces f_i , and surface tractions t_i on the surface Γ , u_i and F are total general nodal vectors of displacement and loading respectively. Obviously C is also the work done by the external forces.

The laminate was divided by $M \times N$ elements, each element was given the value of P_i ($i=1, \dots, M \times N$) which denote macro fiber density variable, when $P=1$ indicates the fiber existence and $P=0$ indicates the fiber inexistence, i.e. base material holds the place. Each element has the same lay-up and fiber volume fraction ρ , thus the practice fiber volume fraction is $P_i \times \rho$ in each element. In order to avoid solving optimization problem with discrete variables, P_i is continuous and should be penalized to steer the P_i to discrete 0-1 values.

After the design domain was divided by elements, the fiber volume constrain is expressed as

$$\sum_{i=1}^{M \times N} \rho \cdot P_i \leq V_0 \cdot (M \times N) \quad (16)$$

where V_0 is the given fiber volume ratio.

The first-order shear deformation theory was used to analyze structural deformation, the formulation of stiffest laminate is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{find} : X &= [P_1, \dots, P_{M \times N}, \rho, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_6, z_1, \dots, z_5] \\ \text{min} : C(X) &= U^T K U \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{M \times N} u_i^T (P_i^\alpha k_i(\rho, x) + (1 - P_i^\alpha) k_i^m) u_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad &\sum_{i=1}^{M \times N} \rho \cdot P_i \leq V_0 \cdot (M \times N) \\ &z_{k-1} - z_k + \beta \leq 0 \\ &0 \leq \rho \leq V_{f \max} \\ &0 \leq \theta_j \leq \pi \\ &-0.5 \leq z_k \leq 0.5 \\ &0 \leq P_i \leq 1 \\ &i = 1, \dots, M \times N; j, k = 1, \dots, 6 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where α is a penal factor, in the context let $\alpha = 3$, k_i^m denotes the stiffness of base material.

5 Numerical examples

Simultaneous optimization designs of layup configuration and fiber distribution using the proposed topology optimization method are presented in this section. The micro lay-up with 6 plies was adopted, owing to discussion above. Analogous simulations with different number of plies were conducted to verify the rationality of the simulation with 6 plies by comparing the numerical results.

Numerical example : The rectangular laminate with one edge clamped. The geometry of laminate was shown in Fig.1. Where $a=20$, $b=10$, $h=0.8$, in-plane concentrated loading $p_1=1$, and out-of-plane concentrated loading $p_2=0.1$. The maximum limited fiber volume ratio is 15% in design domain and the maximum fiber volume fraction in micro lay-up is 0.4. Young's modulus $E_m=3.5$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu_m=0.35$ for base materials. Young's modulus $E_f=73$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu_f=0.22$ for fiber materials.

Fig.1. Design space of the example

Fig.2 showed the optimal distribution of fiber volume in laminates. In Fig.2, the black domain represents laminate material, i.e. the fiber is existence and the white domain represents base material, i.e. the fiber is inexistence. In the black domain, each element has the same lay-up (ply angles and ply thickness) and the fiber volume fraction. The optimal results of compliance and fiber volume fraction, ply angles, plythickness in micro lay-up were shown in table 3.

Fig.2. Optimal distribution of fiber volume in laminates

As for comparison, the micro lay-up with 7 plies, 8 plies and 10 plies were used to design optimization, respectively. The geometry and boundary conditions of laminates are the same as that of the micro lay-up with 6 plies. The optimal results of compliance and fiber volume fraction, ply angles, plythickness in micro lay-up were also shown in table 3.

Table 3 The optimal results of laminates with different piles

n	C	ρ	θ	t
6	10.19	0.274	[0.0/3.9/9.7/76.0/ 164.7/0.1]	[0.220/0.069/0.096/0.135/ 0.279/0.001]
7	10.15	0.333	[0.0/177.8/6.3/74.1/ 64.2/0.0/0.0]	[0.001/0.160/0.208/0.050/ 0.097/0.144/0.140]
8	10.10	0.276	[0.1/177.8/7.9/74.6/ 0.1/164.7/0.1/0.1]	[0.001/0.190/0.170/0.120/ 0.070/0.230/0.001/0.001]
10	10.21	0.322	[0.4/83.2/0.0/0.0/ 76.2/62.1/0/0/0]	[0.360/0.002/0.002/0.004/ 0.040/0.120/0.050/0.060/ 0.080/0.082]

As shown in table 3, the ply thickness could be neglected for it is very small compares with that of other ply thickness and its contribution to the laminate stiffness is also very small when the dimension order of a ply thickness in laminates is 10^{-3} . The two adjacent plies with same ply angles could be equivalent to one ply. The results also indicated that for the case with 6 plies, the ply thickness of outermost layer is 0.001, so this ply layer could be neglected. Thus the optimal lay-up can be realized by 5 plies for the case with 6 plies. It's same for the case with 7 plies, as the first ply thickness is 0.001 in lay-up with 7 plies, and the angles of the outer adjacent two plies are the same, the optimal lay-up of this case also could be realized by 5 plies. The same conclusions were obtained when using the lay-up with 8 and 10 plies, respectively.

Comparing the optimal values of compliance with micro lay-up with different plies, because the relative errors are less than 1%, thus the lay-up with 5 plies can meet the maximum feasible region of lamination parameters well. In order to ensure the conclusion to meet the feasible region better, lay-up with 6 plies was selected to enlarge the design space.

6 Conclusion

The feasible region of lamination parameters increases with the increasing of the number of plies. The feasible region is essentially unchanged when the number of plies is more than 6, i.e. the feasible region which is defined by lamination parameters with 6 plies can be used to approximate the maximum feasible region with 12 lamination parameters. In the optimization process, the micro lay-up was assumed to the same configuration for manufacturing conveniently. Several micro lay-ups with different number of plies were adopted to design the laminates, and the results of numerical examples indicated that the optimal micro lay-up can be realized with 5 plies. In order to meet the feasible region better, lay-up with 6 plies was selected to enlarge the design space is reasonable.

Appendix

16 levels and 12 factors were adopted by Uniform experimental design, the 12 factors were used to represent 12 components of directional vector s . the range of 16 levels was shown as: (-1,-0.9,-0.8,-0.7,-0.6,-0.5,-0.3,-0.1,0.1,0.3,0.5,0.6,0.7,0.8,0.9,1.0).

As vector s should satisfy Eq. (13), the values of 16 levels need to be normalized. Table 4 is the uniform design table.

Table 4 Uniform Design Table $U_{16}(16^{12})$

	k_1^A	k_2^A	k_3^A	k_4^A	k_1^B	k_2^B
1	-0.4096	-0.3687	-0.2867	-0.2458	-0.2048	-0.0410
2	-0.3687	-0.2867	-0.0410	0.1229	0.2458	0.4096
3	-0.3581	-0.2238	0.2686	0.4029	-0.4477	-0.1343
4	-0.2867	-0.0410	0.4096	-0.3277	-0.1229	0.3687
5	-0.2686	0.1343	-0.3581	-0.0448	0.3134	-0.2238
6	-0.2238	0.2686	-0.1343	0.3134	-0.4029	0.3581
7	-0.1343	0.3581	0.2238	-0.4477	-0.0448	-0.2686
8	-0.0410	0.4096	0.3687	-0.2048	0.3277	0.2867
9	0.0410	-0.4096	-0.3687	0.2048	-0.3277	-0.2867
10	0.1343	-0.3581	-0.2238	0.4477	0.0448	0.2686
11	0.2238	-0.2686	0.1343	-0.3134	0.4029	-0.3581
12	0.2686	-0.1343	0.3581	0.0448	-0.3134	0.2238
13	0.2867	0.0410	-0.4096	0.3277	0.1229	-0.3687
14	0.3581	0.2238	-0.2686	-0.4029	0.4477	0.1343
15	0.3687	0.2867	0.0410	-0.1229	-0.2458	-0.4096
16	0.4096	0.3687	0.2867	0.2458	0.2048	0.0410

Cont. table 4 Uniform Design Table $U_{16}(16^{12})$

	k_3^B	k_4^B	k_1^D	k_2^D	k_3^D	k_4^D
1	0.0410	0.1229	0.2867	0.3277	0.3687	0.4096
2	-0.4096	-0.3277	0.0410	0.2048	0.2867	0.3687
3	0.1343	0.3134	-0.2686	-0.0448	0.2238	0.3581
4	-0.3687	-0.2048	-0.4096	-0.2458	0.0410	0.2867
5	0.2238	0.4477	0.3581	-0.4029	-0.1343	0.2686
6	-0.3581	0.0448	0.1343	0.4477	-0.2686	0.2238
7	0.2686	-0.4029	-0.2238	0.3134	-0.3581	0.1343
8	-0.2867	0.2458	-0.3687	0.1229	-0.4096	0.0410
9	0.2867	-0.2458	0.3687	-0.1229	0.4096	-0.0410
10	-0.2686	0.4029	0.2238	-0.3134	0.3581	-0.1343
11	0.3581	-0.0448	-0.1343	-0.4477	0.2686	-0.2238
12	-0.2238	-0.4477	-0.3581	0.4029	0.1343	-0.2686
13	0.3687	0.2048	0.4096	0.2458	-0.0410	-0.2867
14	-0.1343	-0.3134	0.2686	0.0448	-0.2238	-0.3581
15	0.4096	0.3277	-0.0410	-0.2048	-0.2867	-0.3687
16	-0.0410	-0.1229	-0.2867	-0.3277	-0.3687	-0.4096

References

- [1] Zowe J, Kocvara M, Bendsoe MP. Free material optimization via mathematical programming[J]. Mathematical Programming, 1997,79:445-466.
- [2] Rodrigues H, Guedes JM, Bendsoe MP. Hierarchical optimization of material and structure[J]. Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization, 2002, 24:1-10.
- [3] Bendsoe MP, Guedes JM, Haber RB, Pedersen P, Taylor JE. An analytical model to predict optimal material properties in the context of optimal structural design[J]. Journal of Applied Mechanics, 1994,61:930-937.
- [4] Krog LA, Olhoff N. Optimum topology and reinforcement design of disk and plate structures with multiple stiffness and eigenfrequency objectives[J]. Computer and Structures, 1999,72:535-563.
- [5] Jones RM. Mechanics of composite materials(second editon)[M]. Taylor & Francis, 1999
- [6] Hammer VB, Bendsoe MP, Lipton R, Pedersen P. Parametrization in laminate design for optimal compliance[J]. Int J Solids Structure, 1997,34(4):415-434.
- [7] Diaconu CG, Sato M, Sekine H. Feasible region in general design space of laminate on parameters for laminated composites[J]. AI-AA Journal, 2002,40 (3):559-565.
- [8] Setoodeh S, Abdalla MM, Gürdal Z. Approximate feasible regions for lamination parameters [C]. Virginia: Multidisciplinary Analysis and Optimization Conference, 2006.
- [9] Diaconu CG, Sato M, Sekine H. Buckling characteristics and layup optimization of long laminated composite cylindrical shells subjected to combined loads using lamination parameters[J].Composites Structures, 2002,58: 423-433.
- [10] Storn R, Price K. Differential evolution a simple and efficient heuristic for global optimization over continuous spaces[J]. Journal of Global Optimization, 1997,11:341-359.
- [11] Brest J, Boskovic B, Greiner S,e.t. Performance comparison of self-adaptive and adaptive differential evolution algorithms[J]. Soft com puter, 2007,11:617-629.
- [12] Fang KT. Theory and method of the uniform designs [C]. USA: Eighth ISSAT international conference reliability and quality in design, 2002.
- [13] Fang KT, Ma CX. Orthogonal and uniform experimental designs[M]. Beijing: Science Press, 2001.